

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Stroke continues to be a serious healthcare issue that has significant impact on the cognition. Different interventions are available for post-stroke patients to bounce back healthy again after obtaining a number of difficulties due to the stroke. Thus, the objective of this study is to investigate the effect of robotic rehabilitation and conventional rehabilitation on the cognition; specifically, through the domains of general cognition, memory, and attention. **Materials and Methods:** A randomized trial design was used on a sample of post-stroke patients undergoing rehabilitation at Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia and the participants were recruited through convenient sampling. The total number of participants that were obtained are ten; six from the robotic group and four from the conventional group. The participants were assessed twice using Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence – Second Edition (WASI-II), Wechsler Memory Scale – Third Edition Abbreviated (WMS-III), and Comprehensive Trail Making Test (CTMT). The first assessment was done at the initial stage of the intervention and another assessment was done after a one-month duration. **Results:** The outcome of this study found that robotic rehabilitation has a higher improvement in terms of the cognitive domains of memory and attention, as opposed to conventional rehabilitation. **Discussion:** The limitations of this study includes the sample size, accessibility of participants and time limitation. Despite the limitations found throughout the study, the findings have contributed to the understanding of the efficacy of robotic rehabilitation in the aspect of cognition because robotic rehabilitation is fairly new to Malaysia and the contributions of this findings act as a literary contribution to the field of rehabilitation medicine.

Key words: stroke, robotic, rehabilitation, cognition, Malaysia

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is undeniably a serious and disabling health-care issue that has significant impact on the post-stroke patients to continue their daily lives. In fact, stroke survivors may experience the ongoing severe impairments even years following the stroke (1). While the treatments available for stroke are primarily designed for the physical impairments that were produced due to stroke, cognitive impairments are typically reported yet overlooked. Thus, as robotic rehabilitation is fairly new in Malaysia, there is limited amount of study that utilizes the device in the community.

The novelty of this study would provide more evidence and insight into the cognitive profiles of post-stroke individuals that have undergone robotic rehabilitation in Malaysia. The findings of this study would also help to cognitively improve the rehabilitation process of post-stroke patients. Thus, it was hypothesized that the utilization of robotic rehabilitation cognitively improves post-stroke patients compared to the conventional rehabilitation.

Robotic rehabilitation is considered as an effective addition to promote movement among post-stroke patients while controlling the impact of functional capabilities. As robotic therapy is comparatively a newer field of rehabilitation, there is a lack of research available on the experience of the utilization of the device (2). Regardless, post-stroke patients who receive a combination of physiotherapy and robotic therapy are more likely to achieve better results as opposed to those who only receive conventional therapy (3,4).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A randomized trial design was used whereby the robotic group and conventional group are randomly distributed by the Rehab Team from Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia (HUSM). The participants were divided into two groups whereby the robotic group received the robotic rehabilitation and conventional group received the conventional rehabilitation. The study was conducted at the Rehab Unit of Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia which is located in Kubang Kerian, Kelantan.

The inclusion criteria of the participants are as follows: first episode of stroke, hemiparesis resulting from a unilateral ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke, duration of hemiparesis greater than six months, and age range between 20 until 60 years. Whereas the exclusion criteria for the participants are: uncontrolled cardiovascular or respiratory disorders, moderate to severe contracture in the lower extremities, use of pacemaker, cognitive dysfunction (as assessed by MMSE with cut-off score of less than 21), and inability or unwillingness to participate in the study. Regardless, the list of participants was acquired from HUSM's Rehab Team whereby they ensure the criteria are met for each group as the decision for treatment are solely based by the Rehab Team due to their expert knowledge in rehabilitation medicine.

The data was collected at two stages of the progression; the initial stage and the final stage. The data collected at the initial stage measured the cognitive scores of the patients prior to undergoing the rehabilitation whereas the final stage measure the cognitive scores of the patients after one month of undergoing the treatments. For the initial stage, the research tools that were used are as follows: Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE), Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence –

Second Edition (WASI-II), Wechsler Memory Scale – Third Edition Abbreviated (WMS-III), and Comprehensive Trail Making Test (CTMT). The participants were actively involved throughout this study for a duration of one month and the final stage of assessment was conducted with WASI-II, WMS-III and CTMT. The cognitive profile of the participants was based on three components using the three tools: general cognitive functions (WASI-II), memory (WMS-III) and attention (CTMT).

Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. The descriptive statistics method was used to report the demographic profile of the participants. As for the hypotheses, paired sample t-test was used to determine the mean difference between the two groups; robotic and conventional. In other words, the data were analyzed according to the pre and post intervention and was compared between the two groups.

This study has received ethical clearance and was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee USM (HREC) with the code USM/JEPeM/21080568.

RESULTS

The Characteristics of the Participants

This study has a total of ten participants who completed the pre and post assessments, with six participants from the robotic and four participants from the conventional group. Out of the ten participants, 80% were male whereas the 20% were female. The age of the participants ranged between 36 to 59 years with two of them being 58 years old (Table I).

Table I: Participants Demographic Profiles

Variable	n	%
Intervention		
Robotic	6	60
Conventional	4	40
Gender		
Male	8	80
Female	2	20
Age		
36	1	10
38	1	10
39	1	10
43	1	10
45	1	10
46	1	10
54	1	10
58	2	20
59	1	10

General Cognitive Function, Memory and Attention between the Two Groups

The general cognitive functions are measured by using the WASI-II tool and was measured twice on the participants; the first week and the fourth week. Table 2 shows the general cognitive functions of the participants; the general cognitive function is labeled as IQ, the assessment that was conducted in week four is labeled as “post-IQ”, and the assessment that was conducted in

week one is labeled as “pre-IQ”. Table II also shows the memory and attention domains of the participants with the week four labeled as “Post-Memory” and “Post-Attention” whereas week one labeled as “Pre-Memory” and “Pre-Attention” respectively.

Table II: PairedSamples Statistics

Intervention		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	
Robotic (n=6)					
	Pair 1	Post-IQ	78.67	10.13	4.14
		Pre-IQ	73.67	9.77	3.99
	Pair 2	Post-Memory	85.83	7.73	3.16
		Pre-Memory	73.67	11.62	4.74
	Pair 3	Post-Attention	24.17	7.28	2.97
		Pre-Attention	20.33	5.32	2.17
Conventional (n=4)					
	Pair 1	Post-IQ	91.00	10.86	5.43
		Pre-IQ	84.75	7.59	3.79
	Pair 2	Post-Memory	86.25	9.07	4.53
		Pre-Memory	75.00	12.27	6.14
	Pair 3	Post-Attention	24.25	9.18	4.59
		Pre-Attention	24.00	9.42	4.71

The table above represents the findings of the two groups; robotic and conventional. Pair 1, 2, and 3 represents each of the cognitive domains; general cognition, memory and attention. The table above can be used to view the differences clearly and to compare between the two groups as well as to compare between the initial and post assessments.

Table III: Paired Samples Correlations

Intervention		Correlation	Sig.
Robotic (n=6)	Pair 1 Post-IQ & Pre-IQ	.948	.004
	Pair 2 Post-Memory & Pre-Memory	.925	.008
	Pair 3 Post-Attention & Pre-Attention	.856	.029
Conventional (n=4)	Pair 1 Post-IQ & Pre-IQ	.950	.050
	Pair 2 Post-Memory & Pre-Memory	.889	.111
	Pair 3 Post-Attention & Pre-Attention	.999	.001

Table IV: Paired Samples Tests

		Paired Differences			t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean			
Robotic	PostIQ - PreIQ	5.00	3.22	1.32	3.80	5	.013
	PostMemory - PreMemory	12.17	5.34	2.18	5.58	5	.003
	PostAttention - PreAttention	3.83	3.87	1.58	2.43	5	.060
Conventional	PostIQ - PreIQ	6.25	4.35	2.17	2.47	3	.064
	PostMemory - PreMemory	11.25	5.91	2.95	3.81	3	.032
	PostAttention - PreAttention	.250	.500	.250	1.00	3	.391

The tables above represent the summary of paired samples correlations and paired samples test respectively. The correlation can be seen and compared between robotic and conventional groups for each cognitive domain. The significance and mean differences can also be seen and compared between the two groups.

DISCUSSION

As this research looks into cognition through three aspects; general cognition, memory, and attention, each of the aspects were analysed following robotic rehabilitation. The overall findings suggest that it is evident that stroke patients who undergo robotic rehabilitation perform better in terms of their memory and attention ability as opposed to stroke patients who undergo conventional rehabilitation.

General cognition

Based on the data analysis, it was found that the patients who underwent conventional rehabilitation scored higher in general cognitive functions compared to those who underwent robotic rehabilitation. However, it should be acknowledged that the conventional group had a higher initial score for the general cognitive function aspect; thus, the individuals under this group were of better capabilities to complete the treatment. This higher initial score adds as an advantage for the conventional group as opposed to the robotic group. Regardless, both of the treatment groups achieved a considerably high score which is consistent with the past literature which reported the performance of global cognition in post-stroke patients (5).

Memory

The memory domain of the patients' cognitive profile was assessed using WMS-III. Based on the findings, it shows that the patients who underwent robotic rehabilitation scored higher in memory compared to those who underwent conventional rehabilitation. Regardless, the findings suggest

that both of the treatment groups have improved their memory abilities subsequent to undergoing the rehabilitation.

Attention

The attention domain of the patients' cognitive profile was assessed using CTMT. Based on the findings, it was found that patients who underwent robotic rehabilitation improved in the cognitive aspect of attention. Additionally, it was found that the conventional group barely improved in the attention domain. This finding is consistent with the memory domain whereby the conventional group's memory did not improve as much as the robotic group. In fact, past literature reported that an individual's difficulty in paying attention causes poor learning and memory abilities (6). Thus, a poor score on the attention domain is likely the cause for the conventional group to score lower in their memory domain as opposed to the robotic group. This is because for an individual to encode an information in their memory, be it short term or long term memory, the individual must first be able to pay attention to the specific information given first in order for the storage of memory to take place (7).

Regardless, the findings of this study have contributed to the understanding of the efficacy of robotic rehabilitation on post stroke patients. The findings have also yielded the understanding of rehabilitation for stroke patients in the aspect of cognition. But of course, every research has its flaws thus there were a few limitations that were observed during the study. The limitations include sample size, accessibility of the participants, and the time limitations.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, the outcome from this study contributed some noteworthy findings in the fields of clinical neuropsychology and rehabilitation medicine. This study has facilitated in the investigation of the efficacy of robotic rehabilitation and conventional rehabilitation on the cognition. Specifically, in examining the general cognitive functions, memory and attention following robotic rehabilitation. Another contribution of this study is the added information of the comparisons between the cognitive functions, memory and attention between the patients who underwent robotic rehabilitation and the patients who underwent conventional rehabilitation.

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